

INFRASTRUCTURE AND SUSTAINABLE DEVELOPMENT: ISSUES AND CHALLENGES

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A STUDY OF CORPORATE SOCIAL RESPONSIBILITY (CSR) AND RURAL DEVELOPMENT PRACTICES IN SELECTED COMPANIES IN INDIA

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Abstract: *The current study attempts to investigate the practices of Corporate Social Responsibility (CSR) essentially in the rural development background. It assesses the CSR impacts actions on the development socially and economically of rural community. For the intention of the study, Hindalco Industries, Ambuja Cements, Caim India, Lupin and Bajaj Auto, i.e. five Indian companies selected from corporate sector to study their CSR practices in the background of rural development. The research methodology of the current study relied on the internet based investigation; review of literature. The study concludes that Corporate Social Responsibility (CSR) regarded as a significant corporate issue of companies in India irrespective of sector, business goal and size. Hence, CSR activities have constructive impacts not only on rural community development but also in their corporate ethics. The initiative that rural development not only the responsibility of the government but also demands a capable participation from the domestic and international companies. At rest, though a lot had been accomplished within the hypothetical area to build Indian company conscious of ethical rural development with social responsibility of the corporate as an important segment of their corporate activities. However, very not as much of has been accomplished from the time when up to now. The paper is an effort to highlights the importance of social responsibility of the corporate as a tool to make certain better participation of corporate business near rural development.*

Keywords: *Rural development, Corporate Social Responsibility.*

Introduction:

The CSR concept has developed time to time from a religious concept to strategic administration thought; during the procedure of evolution in CSR literature, the same has been understand and defined in a different way inside the social responsibility literature review. Academicians and researchers have philosophically defined corporate social responsibility (CSR) and political influential people have defined CSR in their individual point of view. A few of the examples of different CSR practices and rural development are presented in concise below.

According to McGunie (1916) defined the plan of corporate social responsibility understand that, the Corporate has not only legal and economic commitment but also certain social responsibilities towards the society to which expand further than requirement. Bowen, Howard, R. (1953) opine that theoretical thoughts about CSR way back in 1953 and defined CSR as social responsibility involves the commitment of businessmen to follow those guidelines, to take individuals decisions to pursue those lines of action which are attractive values of our society and in terms of the objectives. CSR means bringing companies performance to the stage, where it is matching with existing social rules and values, norms and expectations (Davis, 1973). Wood (1901) thinks that CSR performance is a industrial organization's pattern of principles of social responsibility procedure and programs, policies and output as they communicate to the corporate social strike back.

Review of Literature:

Although the massive rise in the literature, in modern years, which arrangement with CSR and associated concepts, CSR is still today impossible to simply describe. First, it is due to the information that CSR concept among a comparatively open application convention (Matten and Moon, 2018; Vogel, 2015; and Moon et al., 2015). Secondly, social responsibility is a kind of umbrella, which goes above, or is fitting synonymous by other business-community relations concepts (Matten and Moon, 2028; Matten and Crane, 2005). Lastly, CSR is still especially energetic phenomenon (Matten and Moon, 2008; Asongu, 2007; and Carroll, 1999). Hence, nearby large definitions, which attempt to confine the CSR concept. Content varies and is also frequently possible to see from them, whether acquired in the government sector, the academics sphere, the commercial sector, for example, presented different definitions.

According to European Commission, (2001) CSR is a model whereby corporate incorporate environmental and social concerns in their functions and in their communication with their stakeholders on a voluntarily. Matten and Moon, (2008) at the heart of CSR it is the concept that it replicate the social vital role and the social consequences of corporate achievement.

Carroll (1991) designed and developed CSR model on the basis of argument on 4 foundation, According to his CSR thinking model is made up of the subsequent mechanism in a below order; (i) be profitable-economic responsibility; (ii) obey the law-legal responsibility; (iii) be ethical- ethical responsibility and (iv) be a good international corporate citizen-philanthropic responsibility. Even though the typology classiness of Carrolls, it is inclined to assume a coherent and consistent internal control logic running throughout the different components of CSR. The typology also is inclined to play down the inherent tensions and tradeoffs that exist among these mechanisms. According to coherent of Carroll's model directly and indirectly, a widespread objective in profit oriented-these could be tangible branding and intangible that reputation is visible, and though still it emphasize the vital objective of companies towards maximization of profit (Urmela, 2012, and Kiran and Sharma 2013).

Objective of the study:

- > To highlight the practices of corporate social responsibility and rural development practices of Indian companies.

Methodology of the Study:

Comprehensive review of literature has been done regarding the concepts and topic. The present study has done with the main objectives of understanding and highlight of Hindalco Industries, Ambuja Cements, Cairn India, Lupin and Bajaj Auto of five emerging Indian companies CSR activities with the reference to rural development practices. The study mainly based on secondary sources of information collected from sustainable reports and website of the companies.

Discussion and findings:

- a) Hindalco Industries programmes are aim at provided that rural livelihood in a close by appropriate and eco-sustainable manner through Self-Help Groups (SHGs)-Micro-finance to the farmers and women's of rural area, incorporated agri-development, integrated livestock activity, watershed management, development of micro-enterprise, professional training and skill development throughout Hindalco industries limited. Company has supported infrastructure development throughout the repair with construction of easy approach roads situation up health centres, troughs structures, drinking water also different facilities for the marginalized community, in addition to construction of less cost toilets. Further 43% of water stored in the four dams built by the company at Nagda, that was used for forming and other social purpose for the township and rural community development. Under the 12th finance commission company born 80% of the total cost was to create 3 village infrastructures in the order of Kharach place. In joint venture through district government, the company build 10,023 toilets for BPL families for Chittor district, Armeeyapant Panchayat place. A bus stand to offer service and support to more than 12,500 villagers around Khor was build. The Jal Nirmal venture, carried by the World Bank was completed for around Malkhed with 2 Gram Panchayats covering 10 villages.
- b) Ambuja Cements has established its office in Sarnad Gujarat and has undertaken a needs assessment of the four villages where rural upliftment and developmental work has been projected. Main key matters have been recognized along with preliminary activities have been kick-started throughout participatory ways, as well as a good relationship has been created with the rural villagers. While a part of these actions, less significant members of the rural community were engaged to Ambuja nagar to be introducing to the activities being accomplished there. The villagers have delightful for the work being done there and are keen on having comparable activities in their villages too. Rural development actions in San and had been persistent on water resource management moreover generation of alternating livelihoods.
- c) Caim India undertaken community requirement based projects that get better quality of life in rural areas by setting up quality of education and health care services. The industry given the access to electricity to households of village areas through the solar PV based projects in joint venture with Government. Small group community requirement based projects in remote rural areas to promote locally community development. Increase sustainable rural community and increase income of livelihood through irrigate harvesting and improved performance in farming, livestock and produce market associations. It was expected to increase revenues of over 10,000 farmers in Cairn's functioning neighborhood more than the next five years with program had been executed through NGO partners.
- d) Lupin was set up on 2nd October 1988 year with the objective of providing an alternative model of rural development in the nations, which is sustainable development, replicable and ever developing. Initiating the program of rural development within a less number of 35 villages,

LHWRF has currently accomplish something in invigorating, restoring with recreating living in the 2,200 villages, Uttarakhand, Rajasthan, Maharashtra, and Madhya Pradesh, states of India, which has led to LHWRF rising as one of the major NGOs in the nation. The industry has been victoriously in making a large divergence in the progress of villages of poverty-ridden with particularly in the life of the poorest of the poor as well as empowerment of big number of women in these rural areas. Nowadays, LHWRF on its part is a channel, and an eyewitness of a self-sustaining, self-evolving spectacular conversion.

- e) Bajaj Auto has been undertaken rural development work in selected villages of Maharashtra state, Wardha District and U.P. state in Shikohabad, Dist. Firozabad. The progress actions are undertaken on the basis of the local people need. Extraordinary importance has given on family welfare, healthcare development and immunization, sanitation, supply of good drinking water and alternative source of renewable energy. The industry continued with its rural development actions in Aurangabad and Pune districts of Maharashtra, during JBGVS. JBGVS targets at integrated progress of 43 particular villages, to be conceded out by the villagers beneath their own management with through united efforts imitation by control and state government and local entities with JBGVS performing as a catalyst. Beginning in the April, 2012, it strategy to enhance to the 61 villages, which consist of 11 villages of Sikar District, Rajasthan state, birth place of late Bajaj, Jamnalal, originator of the Bajaj Group of companies with supplementary 13 villages in Aurangabad and Pune districts.

Conclusion:

For delivery, back with progressing the universal balance in the development of economy and society. It has confirmed to think strongly along with act wisely about social responsibility. All Corporate be indebted towards social responsibility of the society, everywhere in widespread, which give it with all substance, natural resources and human being. In the vision of long-term sustainable progress with follow the social responsibility norms, scheduling new rules and functioning efficiently is expected to bring out and sustain equilibrium among corporate world, current generation, future generation, society and nature. As much as the Indian corporate sector is alarmed, it has a long path in fulfilling its social responsibility along with requirement in the direction of the nation and the society. It has accomplished rural progress through the masses to strengthen their lives, to take care for their thoughts in addition to pulverize their ability justifying the affirmation of the organizer.

It is the peak level that the Indian corporate entities should come forward to carry its CSR with following recommendations: (a) Companies CSR goals and government development programs should go hand in hand as national goal; (b) Companies having CSR policies for rural development should have; (i) Dedicated CSR division, (ii) Annual budget allocated, (iii) Well qualified, experienced, and trained professionals; (iv) Better planning, (v) imply and evaluation of CSR; (c) CSR programs should be based on the felt-need of the rural people; (d) participation in the rural program must be enhanced. Furthermore, it is essential to create economic activity and jobs in rural community with a view to strengthen the rural population; (e) Companies should adopt villages and towns with all infrastructural facilities; (f) All companies, NGOs and government should come forward for focusing on senior citizens, disabled/handicapped people, minorities and weaker sections of the society; (g) Government should play the role of motivator, enabler, and facilitator rather than director of corporate social responsibility; (h) Reporting system should be encouraged based activities done in the name of Corporate Social Responsibility highlight the company's commitment for sustainable community development; and (i) Social audit must be conducted by an external agency to assess the social responsibility performance of the corporate with transparency.

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